

Performance of neem-coated urea vis-à-vis ordinary urea applied to irrigated transplanted rice in northwestern India

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The use of neem-coated urea (NCU), produced by spraying neem (*Azadirachta indica*) oil emulsion on prilled urea in the final production stage, can result in high N use efficiency in rice as it contains nitrification-inhibiting properties. Field experiments were conducted from 2005 to 2007 at Ludhiana (sandy loam soil) and Gurdaspur (clay loam soil) in northwestern India to compare the performance of NCU with that of ordinary urea as a source of N for irrigated transplanted rice. Along with a no-N control, the two sources were tested at three N levels: 40%, 80%, and 100% of the recommended level of 120 kg N ha⁻¹ for the region. Fertilizer N was applied in three equal splits at 0, 21, and 42 d after transplanting (DAT). The performance of NCU and ordinary urea was also assessed when these were applied on the basis of plant need as reflected by the color of the first fully opened leaf from the top. Leaf color was compared with a six-panel leaf color chart (LCC) manufactured by Nitrogen Parameters, Chennai (India), following IRRI specifications. In these treatments, a dose of 20 kg N ha⁻¹ was applied at 7 DAT. The color of the rice leaves was monitored weekly starting at 14 DAT. Whenever the color intensity of the first fully opened leaf from the top was less than that indicated by shade 4 of the LCC, N (either urea or NCU) was applied at 30 kg ha⁻¹. Nine treatments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications (see table). A basal dose consisting of 26 kg P ha⁻¹ and 50 kg K ha⁻¹ was applied to all plots before transplanting. Cultivars PR118 at Ludhiana and PR116 at Gurdaspur were used in the 3-year study. Four-week-old seedlings of rice were transplanted at 20 × 15-cm spacing in 30-m² treatment plots. At maturity, grain and straw yields were recorded. Grain and straw samples were analyzed for moisture content and total N content. Grain yield was reported at 14% moisture content. Total N uptake by the grain and straw was calculated (see table). Statistical analysis of the 3-year pooled data was carried out using IRRISTAT version 5.0. The year × treatment effects were not significant, suggesting that the treatments had the same effect each year.

Application of N through NCU or ordinary urea up to 120 kg N ha⁻¹ significantly increased rice grain yield in both Ludhiana and Gurdaspur (see table). When applied in three equal splits at 0, 21, and 42 DAT, the NCU did not outperform urea in terms of grain yield or N uptake at all N application levels in both locations. The only exception was at Ludhiana when NCU and urea were applied at 120 kg N ha⁻¹. The NCU treatment had 5.6% higher grain yield, significantly higher than that produced using ordinary urea. At Ludhiana, NCU use resulted in higher recovery and agronomic efficiencies than at Gurdaspur. These results suggest the greater impact of nitrification inhibition in the coarse-textured Ludhiana soil than in the fine-textured Gurdaspur soil. This effect became more visible with real-time N management using the LCC. The use of NCU not only resulted in a significantly higher grain yield and N uptake at Ludhiana; it also exhibited higher recovery and agronomic efficiencies than those observed with the ordinary urea treatment. In contrast, in Gurdaspur's clay loam soil, LCC-based NCU and urea application showed the same results for yield, N uptake, and fertilizer use efficiency. The data further showed that real-time N management using an LCC can lead to substantial savings in fertilizer-N use, as the yields obtained following blanket recommendations (i.e., fixed dose and fixed timing of fertilizer-N application) were similar.

Grain yield, N uptake, and fertilizer-N use efficiencies of rice as influenced by neem-coated urea (NCU) and urea treatment following fixed-time application or leaf color chart (LCC)-guided need-based application, Ludhiana and Gurdaspur, India, 2005-07 (pooled data over 3 years).

Source, rate, and time of N application (DAT kg N ha ⁻¹)*	Total N applied (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Total N uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	Recovery efficiency (%)	Agronomic efficiency kg grain (kg ha N) ⁻¹
<i>Ludhiana</i>					
No-N control	0	3.86	53	–	–
016, 2116, 4216 urea	48	5.21	74	43.8	28.1
032, 2132, 4232 urea	96	5.99	98	46.9	22.2
040, 2140, 4240 urea	120	6.38	114	50.8	21.0
016, 2116, 4216 NCU	48	5.29	80	56.3	29.8
032, 2132, 4232 NCU	96	6.25	106	55.2	24.9
040, 2140, 4240 NCU	120	6.74	118	54.2	24.0
720, 2130, 3530, 5630 LLC4 (urea)	110	6.15	98	40.9	20.8
720, 2130, 3530, 5630 LLC4 (NCU)	110	6.68	106	48.0	25.6
	LSD (0.05)	0.351	7.1		
<i>Gurdaspur</i>					
No-N control	0	4.06	63	–	–
016, 2116, 4216 urea	48	5.37	91	58.3	27.3
032, 2132, 4232 urea	96	6.11	113	52.1	21.4
040, 2140, 4240 urea	120	6.49	125	51.7	20.3
016, 2116, 4216 NCU	48	5.43	92	60.4	28.5
032, 2132, 4232 NCU	96	6.32	114	53.1	23.5
040, 2140, 4240 NCU	120	6.65	124	50.8	21.6
720, 2830, 4230 LLC4 (urea)	80	6.49	112	61.3	30.4
720, 2830, 4230, LLC4 (NCU)	80	6.61	118	68.8	31.9
	LSD (0.05)	0.284	9.1		

*DAT = days after transplanting of rice.